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Exploring social sustainability in emerging battery technologies

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Abstract

- *Energy transitions are increasingly considered from the angle of multidisciplinary and multidimensionality;*
- *Recent initiatives, such as Critical Raw Material act or Global Battery Passport support the Social Sciences and Humanities role;*
- *We examined the different aspects of SSH integration into clean energy transition/battery research with the help of modified seven questions' technique during an exploratory digital workshop;*
- *As a result, we identified a common base to integrate SSH into battery development;*
- *The social sustainability' integration into battery research considers different life cycle stages, technology and human readiness levels.*

Keywords: battery technology research, energy storage, environmental, social, economic and human sustainability, socially responsible HRM (SRHRM), sustainability

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